

IMPROVED EQUIPMENT FOR DRYING HIGH-GRADE COTTON

A.A.Ismailov

Prof., assist.

Ismailov I.D.

Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry

PhD, docent, Bakhtiyor Karshiev

Termez Institute of Engineering and Technology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14988867>

Annotation. In the article, studies of existing cotton drying equipment with a drum design showed that they have a number of drawbacks. As a result of the analysis of the cotton drying process and the study of the demand for the drying process, a new resource-saving drying equipment was proposed, which increases the efficiency of the cotton drying process.

Keywords: heat, cotton, drying, improved, hot air, drum, tape.

Аннотация. В статье исследования существующего оборудования для сушки хлопка с барабанной конструкцией показали, что оно имеет ряд недостатков. В результате анализа процесса сушки хлопка и изучения спроса на процесс сушки было предложено новое ресурсосберегающее сушильное оборудование, повышающее эффективность процесса сушки хлопка

Ключевые слова: тепло, хлопок, сушка, усовершенствованный, горячий воздух, барабан, лента.

In recent years, large-scale measures have been implemented in our republic to develop energy- and resource-saving technologies for growing and processing cotton, and certain results have been achieved. The main quality indicators of the fiber obtained from the processing of raw cotton depend on the humidity at which it was initially processed, and the drying process is the main technological process in the processing of cotton [1].

It is known that currently in the cotton processing industry, all cotton is dried using drum drying equipment, without paying attention to the variety and initial moisture content of cotton. This leads to an increase in the cost of products manufactured during processing.

In addition, considering that the moisture content of high-grade cotton supplied to the production process is not high, the conducted studies have shown that drying cotton in existing drying drums is economically inefficient in terms of energy and heat loss to the environment [2-8].

Taking the above into account, based on the study of the current drying process, an improved drying unit was developed for low-moisture and seed cotton.

The improved cotton drying equipment works as follows (figure):

Cotton is fed to the drying unit (1) by means of feed rollers onto a rotating belt. The cotton is dropped onto the surface of the belt (6). When the cotton moves on the surface of the belt, the hot air entering the drying unit from the supply pipe (7) meets with the wet cotton on the surface of the belt, as a result of which the cotton heats up and the moisture in it evaporates.

1 - base of the improved drying unit, 2 - feed rollers, 3 - guide, 4 - belt drive rollers, 5 - cotton outlet chute of the cotton drying unit, 6 - belt, 7 - heat supply pipe of the drying unit, 8 - belt lifting rollers, 9 - grid installed at the heat input.

Figure. Improved cotton drying equipment

When the cotton reaches the end of the first strip, it falls on the surface of the lower strip due to the rotation of the strip. After this, the cotton is moved in the opposite direction along the second row of strips, where the cotton drying process is carried out, as in the above strip.

The same process is repeated on the tapes in the lower rows. The belts are set in motion by rollers (4). At the end of the process, the dried cotton is discharged from the drying unit through a chute (5). Used hot air from the drying equipment is discharged through the exhaust pipe. The degree and speed of cotton drying, the time the cotton is in the drying equipment, the temperature of the hot air supplied for drying the cotton, and the belt speed can be adjusted.

The use of this drying equipment leads to resource savings and preservation of cotton quality indicators when drying low-moisture and seed cotton.

References:

1. I.D.Ismoilov., Sh.Sh. Hakimov., A.A. Ismailov. “Hozirgi kunda klaster tizimidagi paxta tozalash korxonalarida paxtani quritishda energiya tejamkor texnologiyasini tadqiqoti”. TTESI. Toshkent 2023.
2. Kupalova Yu., Usmankulov A. Choosing the optimum regime for drying raw cotton in drum drier. // American Journal of Research. USA/Michigan. 2018 й, №9-10, -P.172-178.
3. Azimjon Parpiev, Ilkhom Sabirov, Kamoliddin Yakubov, Ibrokhim Ismoilov, Bakhtiyor Karshiev “The effect of drum drying temperature on the moisture of cotton components” Ann. For. Res. 65(1). 2022.
4. Парпиев А. П., Каршиев Б. Э. РАВНОМЕРНОСТЬ СУШКИ КОМПОНЕНТОВ ХЛОПКА-СЫРЦА //Universum: технические науки. – 2022. – №. 9-2 (102). – С. 51-54.
5. Каршиев Б. Э. и др. Пахтани тозалашга тайёрлаш технологиясининг таҳлили //RESULTS OF NATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 6.
6. Каршиев Б.Э., Парпиев А.П., Хушбаков А.Н. Анализ температуры, влажности волокна и семян в технологических процессах на хлопкоочистительных предприятиях// INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE: YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS, 2022 Prague, Czech. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7117865>.
7. Қаршиев БЭ П. А. П. Пахта ва уни компонентларини қатламда қуритиш тадқиқоти //ЎзМУ хабарлари. Илмий журнал. ISSN. – С. 2181-7324.
8. Қаршиев БЭ П. А. П., Сайидова М. Ҳ. Пахтани қатламда қуритишнинг аэродинамик режимларини аниқлаш тадқиқоти //Фан ва технологиялар тараққиёти. Илмий-техникавий ва амалий журнал. Бухоро. ISSN. – С. 2181-8193.